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Integrated indoor hygiene concept in a kindergarten living lab: effects on microbial load and infection-related absenteeism

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Introduction: Effective infection prevention and control (IPC) in buildings requires integrated strategies addressing air, surfaces, and water systems.

Methods: This study evaluated the impact of an Indoor Hygiene Concept (IHC) on microbial contamination and infection-related absenteeism in a real-world kindergarten setting. A Living Lab intervention was conducted, where one unit implemented antimicrobial coatings, antimicrobial blue light technology, and a portable air purifier, while a comparable control unit remained unchanged. Environmental sampling of high-touch surfaces ($n = 368$ per unit), monitoring of infection-related absences among children aged 3–5 years and staff, and continuous indoor air quality assessment were performed between 2023 and 2025.

Results: Baseline environmental and hygiene conditions were comparable between units. Antimicrobial coatings reduced mean surface microbial load (9.4 vs. 15.9 CFU/cm²), although median values were similar, indicating very limited effects under high baseline hygiene conditions. The intervention unit showed a consistent but not statistically significant reduction in infection-related absenteeism (19% in staff and 12% in children).

Discussion: These results suggest that integrated indoor hygiene solutions may support infection control in real-world settings. More extensive studies, including larger human study populations, and viral measurements are needed to confirm these preliminary observations and evaluate long-term sustainability.

KEYWORDS

absenteeism, air purification, antimicrobial surfaces, built environment, indoor hygiene, kindergarten, living lab, microbial contamination

1 Introduction

Infectious diseases remain a major contributor to global morbidity and mortality and impose a substantial economic burden on society. Consequently, effective strategies to prevent infection transmission are increasingly important. As people spend a large proportion of their time indoors, the role of indoor environments in shaping transmission dynamics has gained growing attention. Public indoor spaces, in particular, serve as hubs for human interaction and may facilitate the spread of infectious agents. In response, a growing body of research has focused on developing solutions to mitigate infection transmission within built environments (Zhang et al., 2022; Salonen et al., 2023). However, despite their practical potential, the antimicrobial and infection prevention and

control (IPC) efficacy of these solutions has been evaluated in relatively few studies under real-world conditions, as highlighted in recent reviews on antimicrobial coatings and light-based technologies (Pereira-Silva et al., 2025; Ubaldi et al., 2024; Ozdemir et al., 2025).

Following the COVID-19 pandemic, research has increasingly emphasized the importance of indoor air quality and ventilation in controlling respiratory virus transmission, revealing that most buildings were not originally designed with infection control as a priority (Morawska et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2022). While improvements in building operation - particularly better ventilation - can reduce infection risk, evidence suggests that effective mitigation requires coordinated, multi-measure strategies rather than reliance on single interventions. Moreover, pathogens can spread not only via airborne transmission but also through contaminated surfaces and water systems (Dai et al., 2017), highlighting the need for comprehensive approaches to IPC in indoor environments.

To address this complexity, the concept of indoor hygiene has been proposed as a framework for integrating infection prevention measures across different components of the built environment (Salonen et al., 2022). The Indoor Hygiene Concept (IHC) considers air, surfaces, and water systems as interconnected pathways for microbial transmission and promotes the use of engineering and antimicrobial solutions to reduce exposure. Many of these solutions are designed to operate independently of user behaviour, thereby reducing reliance on consistent human compliance. Effective implementation of IHC requires coordinated efforts across the building lifecycle, involving architects, engineers, facility managers, and cleaning personnel (Salonen et al., 2023).

In addition to potential health benefits, investments in infection prevention solutions - such as antimicrobial materials and improved ventilation - may yield long-term economic advantages by reducing healthcare costs and productivity losses associated with illness-related absences (Cutler and Summers, 2020; Falkinham, 2020; Abraham et al., 2021; Morawska et al., 2021). However, there remains a notable gap in the literature regarding the real-world effectiveness and economic implications of comprehensive indoor hygiene strategies.

In the present study, a Living Lab indoor hygiene intervention was implemented in a kindergarten to evaluate the impact of an integrated IHC. The specific objectives were to (i) define and implement a set of IHC solutions and monitoring methods, (ii) assess microbial load on high-touch surfaces, in drinking water, and in indoor air, and (iii) evaluate effects on the incidence of acute gastrointestinal and respiratory infections among children and staff.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Description of kindergarten living lab

The kindergarten Living Lab investigated in this study was in Satakunta region in southwestern Finland, in a coastal area of the Baltic Sea. This study was founded on previous Living Lab research conducted by our group (Inkinen et al., 2017) and was approved by the Ethics Committee for Human Sciences of Satakunta Universities. Permission to conduct the study on-site was granted by the City of

Ulvila, which was responsible for the administration of the kindergarten.

The Living Lab consisted of two comparable units: one intervention unit and one control unit. The kindergarten building was a two-storey structure that was renovated between 2022 and 2023. Both units were located on the second floor and shared access to common areas, including a mudroom, an outdoor garment vestibule, and an entrance to an upper playground. The layouts of the units were identical but mirrored (Supplementary Figure 1). Each unit comprised a main play and lunchroom, a restroom, a bathroom, a separate playroom, and a coat rack area. The main playroom and restroom could be connected or separated using an accordion door.

Both units included children aged 3–5 years and were designed for 20 children and three staff members. Daily care activities were conducted during standard operating hours (06:00–17:00). Personnel and daily activities were organized separately for each unit to minimize cross-contact between groups to prevent microbes and parasites, e.g., head lice, from spreading between groups.

Building systems and environmental conditions were comparable between the units. During the first year of the study, drinking water was supplied from chemically purified groundwater; this was later replaced by chemically purified artificial groundwater. The primary piping material was copper. Ventilation was provided by a constant air volume system with heated supply air, supplemented by air-to-air heat pumps for cooling. Ventilation operated continuously, with reduced airflow after 18:00 when there were no users on the premises. Filters were replaced twice annually.

Cleaning practices were standardized across both units. Daily cleaning was performed on weekdays (Mon-Fri) after operating hours by trained personnel, with additional weekly and monthly cleaning of less frequently addressed surfaces (e.g., upper surfaces). Immediate cleaning was conducted in response to visible contamination. Surfaces were cleaned using microfiber cloths and a mildly alkaline general-purpose cleaner, while sanitary facilities were cleaned using a mildly acidic agent. The same cleaning staff were responsible for both units to ensure consistency.

2.2 Indoor hygiene interventions and monitoring

In this study, the selection of indoor hygiene interventions was based on their reported effectiveness, safety, and suitability for use in kindergarten environments. All selected solutions were commercially available at the time of implementation. The following interventions were installed in the intervention unit:

- A portable air purification device based on electrostatic filtration ($n = 1$).
- Silver-based antimicrobial door handles installed on frequently used doors ($n = 12$); the antimicrobial coating was integrated during manufacturing.
- TiO₂-based photocatalytic coating applied as a spray to frequently touched surfaces, including tables ($n = 4$), chairs ($n = 20$), handles ($n = 4$), touchless faucets ($n = 3$), toilet flush buttons ($n = 2$), locker doors ($n = 20$), light switches ($n = 1$), and

TABLE 1 The number of samples collected from kindergarten Living Lab in a single sampling session.

Sampling location	Number of samples intervention + control
Door handle	12 + 12
Wire handle	4 + 4
Table surface	4 + 4
Chair backrest	4 + 4
Touchless faucet	3 + 3
Sink	3 + 3
Toilet flush button	2 + 2
Light switch	1 + 1
Locker door	2 + 2
Total	35 + 35

Bold values indicates to total number of samples in a single sampling session.

basins (n = 3). The coating was activated under standard indoor lighting conditions.

- Antimicrobial blue light installed in a storage unit for toys and other shared items (n = 1).

The control unit included the same types and number of surfaces without antimicrobial treatments.

Indoor environmental conditions were continuously monitored in both units. Measured parameters included temperature, relative humidity, carbon dioxide (CO₂), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and particulate matter (PM₁–PM₁₀). Measurements were conducted using commercially available monitoring devices (Airwits, Miran) and a custom-built AQ1 system assembled from commercial sensor modules.

Occupancy-related activity was estimated using an electronic motion sensor installed at the entrance of a toilet cubicle. The sensor placement was designed to capture user presence while minimizing interference from unrelated movement.

The installation timelines for the indoor hygiene interventions are provided in [Supplementary Figure 2](#).

2.3 Microbiological analyses

2.3.1 Sampling

Microbial samples were collected from indoor air, drinking water, and frequently touched surfaces in both the intervention and control units. Sampling was conducted simultaneously in both units to ensure comparability. A total of eleven sampling campaigns were carried out between March 2023 and September 2025 at approximately three-month intervals. In total, 737 samples were collected. The sampling locations are presented in [Table 1](#) and the schedule in [Supplementary Figure 2](#).

Surface samples were collected from predefined locations ([Table 1](#)) using cotton swabs in accordance with ISO 18593:2018 ([International Organization for Standardization, 2018](#)). Prior to sampling, swabs were moistened in 5 mL of Dey-Engley (D/E)

neutralizing solution (BioTrading Benelux B.V.; Liofilchem S. r.l., Italy). Sampling was performed either over the entire surface or within a defined area using a template. Each surface was swabbed in three directions to ensure adequate coverage. After sampling, swabs were returned to the collection tubes and transported to the laboratory for analysis.

Water samples were collected from faucets in accordance with ISO 19458:2006, section 4.4.1.5 (“water as consumed”). Sampling was performed without prior flushing or disinfection of the outlet to reflect typical usage conditions.

Air samples were collected using a Surface Air System (SAS SUPER IAQ, VWR®) impactor. Air was sampled directly onto TSA TLHTh agar plates (VWR®), with a sampled volume of 250 L per sample.

2.3.2 Plating and microbial analyses

Surface samples were processed immediately after collection according to [Inkinen et al. \(2017\)](#). Prior to analysis, samples were vortexed for 2 min. Total microbial counts were determined using TC Compact Dry plates (Shimadzu Diagnostics Corporation, Japan). Duplicate plating was performed using 1 mL of sample per plate. In addition, diluted samples (1:19 dilution in phosphate-buffered saline, PBS; VWR®) were plated in parallel. Plates were incubated at 20 °C ± 1 °C for 5 days, and results were expressed as colony-forming units per surface area (CFU/cm²). The method detects aerobic bacteria, molds, and yeasts.

Indicator organism analysis was conducted using an enrichment-based approach. A 1 mL aliquot of each sample was inoculated into 9 mL of Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth (Neogen Corporation, USA) and incubated at 36 °C ± 1 °C for 3 days. After enrichment, 1 mL of each culture was plated onto selective Compact Dry media: EC plates for coliforms and *Escherichia coli*, ETC plates for *Enterococcus*, and XSA plates for *Staphylococcus aureus* (Shimadzu Diagnostics Corporation, Japan). Plates were incubated at 36 ± 1 °C for 24 h. Results were recorded qualitatively as presence or absence.

Water samples were analysed for *Legionella pneumophila* using the IDEXX Legiolert® system (IDEXX Laboratories, USA) in accordance with the manufacturer’s instructions ([IDEXX Laboratories, 2017](#)), [Checa et al. \(2021\)](#). Heterotrophic plate counts at 22 °C were determined following ISO 6222:1999 using IDEXX Easy Disc YEA plates. All water samples were processed immediately after collection.

Air samples were incubated on TSA TLHTh agar plates at 20 °C ± 1 °C for 5 days. Results were expressed as colony-forming units per sampled air volume.

2.4 Data collection on the incidence of infectious diseases

Data on infection-related absenteeism associated with acute respiratory and gastrointestinal symptoms, were collected anonymously in electronic format. Data were aggregated monthly at the unit level and recorded separately for children and staff members. It included the total number of persons and the number of infection-related absenteeism days in the unit. The period of data collection spanned from April 2023 to November

2025 and included all months during which the kindergarten was in operation, excluding summer closure periods. Absence data were obtained from routine administrative records maintained by the kindergarten.

Concerning the staff in kindergarten, the definition of infection related absenteeism referred only to acute respiratory and gastrointestinal symptoms. This information was reported by staff superior who had access to the absenteeism information, and she only reported these two categories.

The same superior person of kindergarten had access to the absenteeism information of children provided by the parents. There were several categories of absenteeism, e.g., holiday or scheduled absenteeism (part-time care). One of these categories was sick days. This data on sick days did not include specific information on the cause of the illness. However, sick days of children in this age range are typically caused by acute respiratory and gastrointestinal infections. This is especially the case in Finland, where majority of babies are vaccinated against most common virus-related infections (Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare, 2026). Some of the sick days could be explained by a chronic illness (e.g., asthma), but these are likely marginal within this age range. Thus, in this study, an assumption was made that the vast majority of sick days were caused by respiratory and gastrointestinal infections.

2.5 Statistical analysis

Microbial data were analysed using the Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric test with Holm-Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons. A non-parametric approach was selected because the data did not meet normality assumptions, even after transformation.

The primary analysis was conducted using the full dataset. In addition, subgroup analyses were performed by categorizing samples according to location (toilets, group room surfaces, and door handles) and sampling time (11 sampling campaigns). These subgroup analyses were conducted to explore potential spatial and temporal variation, including seasonal effects. Comparisons were made both between the intervention and control units and within subgroups.

Infection-related absenteeism was calculated as the monthly proportion of sick days relative to total working or care days per unit. Even though the number of persons in the units differed between months, it did not show as such in the monthly averages of infection-related absenteeism. The number of people, however, increased the monthly working and care days. Differences between the intervention and control units were assessed using the Kruskal-Wallis test due to non-normal distribution of the data. In addition, for differences in the months without recorded infection-related absenteeism were tested using χ^2 -test.

3 Results

3.1 Microbial load in air and water

Microbial samples from indoor air and water were collected between March 2023 and September 2025. A total of 39 indoor air samples were analysed. Indoor air quality monitoring indicated no

TABLE 2 Percentage of surface samples exceeding 20 CFU/cm², which could be considered as the limit value for dirty surfaces in buildings of this type of use (Sneed et al., 2004), and 2.5 CFU/cm², which is the reference value for surface hygiene in hospitals (Mulvey et al., 2011).

Group	N	> 2.5 CFU/cm ²	> 20 CFU/cm ²
All	737	41.7%	8.8%
Intervention	369	40.1%	9.5%
Control	368	43.2%	8.2%

notable differences between the intervention and control units, and measured parameters followed expected seasonal variation typical for Finnish conditions. No indicators of moisture damage-associated microbial growth were detected in the air samples. Overall, these findings confirm that the environmental conditions in the two units were comparable.

In addition to routine monitoring conducted by local health authorities, water samples were collected for *Legionella* analysis (n = 8). *Legionella* spp. were detected at concentrations below the action threshold defined in the EU Drinking Water Directive 2020/2184 (2020), indicating no *Legionella* risk related to water systems during the study period.

3.2 Microbial load on surfaces

In most surface samples, microbial counts were low in both units. Specifically, 91.8% of control samples and 90.5% of samples from antimicrobial-coated surfaces showed microbial levels at or below 20 CFU/cm² (Table 2), a commonly used threshold for surface cleanliness in non-clinical environments (Sneed et al., 2004). Similarly, 56.8% of control samples and 59.9% of antimicrobial-coated samples were at or below 2.5 CFU/cm², corresponding to a benchmark for high surface hygiene in healthcare settings (Mulvey et al., 2011).

The mean microbial count was lower on antimicrobial-coated surfaces (9.4 CFU/cm²) compared to control surfaces (15.9 CFU/cm²) (Figure 1; Table 3), whereas median values were statistically speaking identical (1.9 CFU/cm² vs. 2.0 CFU/cm²). The distribution of values was skewed, with a small number of higher observations in the control group influencing the mean. Due to non-normal data distribution, comparisons were based on Kruskal-Wallis' (Mann-Whitney) non-parametric tests, which showed no statistically significant differences between the medians of the intervention and control groups.

Subgroup analysis by surface location (toilets, group room surfaces, and door handles) also revealed no statistically significant differences between the intervention and control units. A comparison across all six subgroups (intervention and control within each location) indicated a statistically significant difference in rank distributions; however, this difference was not associated with a consistent pattern favouring either intervention or control conditions.

Indicator organisms representing faecal (*Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus*) and skin (*Staphylococcus aureus*) contamination were analysed qualitatively (presence/absence). Overall, 43.4% of samples were positive for at least one indicator organism (Table 4), with similar proportions observed on antimicrobial-coated surfaces

FIGURE 1 Total microbial count (CFU/cm²) in antimicrobial coated (intervention) and control surfaces. X represents the mean value. The line inside the box represents the median value. The box shows the middle 50% of the data (IQR = Interquartile Range): the bottom represents Q1 (25th percentile) and the top represents Q3 (75th percentile). Whiskers: Lines extending from the box to the minimum (Q1-1.5*IQR) and maximum (Q3+1.5*IQR) values. Outliers are individual points plotted beyond the whiskers, representing extreme values. (A) Focuses on the IQR, median and mean values. In (B), the results are plotted on a logarithmic scale so that outliers can be shown on the same scale as the other results.

TABLE 3 Summary Statistics for microbial counts (CFU/cm²).

Microbial count (CFU/cm ²)	Antimicrobial coated surface	Control surface
Number of samples	369	368
Average	9.38	15.89
Standard deviation	28.89	106.44
Coefficient of variation	308.12%	669.95%
Minimum	0.02	0.00
Maximum	323.11	1787.50
Range	323.09	1787.50
Standardized skewness	50.09	109.60
Standardized kurtosis	202.09	857.75

(44.2%) and control surfaces (42.7%). Comparable results were observed for toilet surfaces (Table 5).

The occurrence of multiple indicators per sample was lower on antimicrobial-coated surfaces. Across all samples, 38 antimicrobial surface samples contained at least two indicators, compared to 47 samples in the control group. In toilet areas, the corresponding values were 10 and 22, respectively.

The prevalence of *Enterococcus* was similar between antimicrobial and control surfaces (23.0% vs. 23.4%; Figure 2A), including in toilet areas (21.1% vs. 22.4%; Figure 2B). *S. aureus* was detected less frequently on antimicrobial-coated surfaces (15.4% vs. 19.0%; toilet areas: 14.5% vs. 21.1%), whereas *E. coli* was

detected more frequently (16.3% vs. 13.0%; toilet areas: 15.8% vs. 11.2%).

3.3 Effect of indoor hygiene concept on incidence of infectious diseases

3.3.1 Children

During the follow-up period, infection-related absenteeism was observed in all months, with no months entirely free of illness among children. The proportion of sick days was lower in the intervention unit compared to the control unit (4.4% vs. 5.0%), corresponding to a relative reduction of 12%. However, this difference was not statistically significant.

The number of children in each unit varied over time (range: 15–41), depending on seasonal attendance and operational arrangements. In some instances, the two groups were temporarily combined. However, the number of persons is not directly seen in the monthly averages of infection-related absenteeism, as explained in Section 2.5. Temporal variation in absenteeism followed expected seasonal patterns, with lower proportions of sick days during summer months. The temporal trends were similar in both units (Figure 3). No data were available for July 2023 and July 2025 due to summer closure, and data for April 2024 were missing due to a miscommunication.

3.3.2 Staff members

Among staff, months without recorded infection-related absenteeism were more frequent in the intervention unit

TABLE 4 Number and proportion of samples positive for indicator bacteria on antimicrobial (intervention) and control surfaces.

Group	All		Positive indicators		Number of positive indicators per sample			
	N	Number	Number	Proportion (%)	0	1	2	3
All	737	320	320	43.4%	417	235	83	2
Intervention	369	163	163	44.2%	206	125	37	1
Control	368	157	157	42.7%	211	110	46	1

TABLE 5 Number and proportion of samples positive for indicator bacteria on antimicrobial (intervention) and control surfaces in toilet area.

Group	Positive indicators			Number of positive indicators per sample			
	All N	Number	Proportion (%)	0	1	2	3
All	304	128	42.1%	176	96	31	1
Intervention	152	67	44.1%	85	57	9	1
Control	152	61	40.1%	91	39	22	0

(16 months) than in the control unit (9 months). This result was not statistically significant. The overall proportion of sick days was lower in the intervention unit (2.5%) compared to the control unit (3.1%), corresponding to a relative reduction of 19%; however, this difference was also not statistically significant. However, the number of observed staff members was very small.

As observed for children, absenteeism among staff also showed seasonal variation, with lower values during summer months. The kindergarten was closed in July 2023 and July 2025 (Figure 4).

4 Discussion

In this study, an indoor hygiene Living Lab was established in a kindergarten to evaluate the impact of an integrated indoor hygiene

concept (IHC) on microbial contamination and infection-related absenteeism among children and staff. The intervention combined a portable air purification device, antimicrobial surface coatings and an antimicrobial blue light device, while a comparable control unit to which no such solutions had been applied was monitored simultaneously within the same building under similar conditions.

The overall incidence of infection-related absences was low in both units during the study period, and no major outbreaks were observed. Infection related absenteeism was numerically lower in the intervention group compared to the control group, but the difference was not statistically significant. This consistent directional trend suggests a potential effect of the intervention, but more data would be needed to confirm this. However, these findings must be interpreted with caution. The study was likely underpowered due to the relatively small and dynamic human population, absence of individual-level longitudinal data, and the use of non-parametric statistical methods necessitated by non-normal data distributions. These factors increase variability and reduce sensitivity to detect small effects. Nevertheless, the observed trend is consistent with previous findings reporting reduced morbidity associated with air purification in kindergarten environments (Vartiainen et al., 2024).

The contribution of antimicrobial surface coatings seems to have no effect on microbial counts. The mean surface microbial load was 9.4 CFU/cm² in the intervention group and 15.9 CFU/cm² in the control group. However, there were two possible outlier values in the control group and if they were removed the average dropped to 8.9 CFU/cm². Contamination levels were consistently low in both units throughout the study period. Therefore, we consider it unlikely that increasing the sample size alone would substantially alter the overall interpretation of these findings.

Analysis of indicator organisms revealed no consistent advantage of antimicrobial surfaces. While *S. aureus* was detected

less frequently on antimicrobial-coated surfaces, *E. coli* showed higher prevalence, and *Enterococcus* levels were comparable between groups. These results suggest species-specific responses to antimicrobial interventions rather than a uniform reduction in microbial contamination. *E. coli*, a commensal bacterium of the human gastrointestinal tract, is highly abundant and is commonly used as an indicator of faecal contamination on environmental surfaces, particularly in sanitary settings where inadequate hand hygiene may occur. In contrast, *S. aureus* is typically present on the skin at lower abundance but represents a clinically relevant opportunistic pathogen. Therefore, the observed reduction in *S. aureus* prevalence on antimicrobial surfaces is of particular importance. However, it is important to note that viral contamination - recognized as the primary driver of gastrointestinal and respiratory infections in kindergarten settings (Andrup, et al., 2024) - was not assessed in this study due to methodological constraints. Since no major outbreaks were observed during the 3.5-year study period, the concentrations of infectious viruses on environmental contact surfaces were expected to remain very low. This limits conclusions regarding overall infection transmission dynamics.

The observed reduction in infection-related absenteeism cannot be attributed to a single component of the intervention, as the IHC consisted of multiple simultaneous measures, including air purification, antimicrobial lighting, and antimicrobial surfaces. Nevertheless, the integrated nature of the intervention reflects real-world implementation conditions, where multiple strategies are typically applied in combination. This aligns with current infection prevention guidance for kindergartens emphasizing layered approaches, including ventilation, cleaning, and hygiene practices (CDC, 2025). Interventions that rely on human behaviour like cleaning and hand hygiene are inherently variable and may be compromised during periods of high workload or increased infection pressure. In this context, built-in, human-independent hygiene solutions like effective antimicrobial coatings may provide an additional layer of protection by reducing dependence on consistent user compliance and supporting baseline infection control.

Previous cost analyses of similar set-up in elderly care Living Labs indicate that substantial reductions in sickness-related absences

are required to offset investments (Repka et al., 2026), underscoring the importance of measurable health outcomes for cost-effectiveness. Indirect societal benefits, such as reduced parental absenteeism and improved productivity, may further increase value but were not assessed here. From a sustainability perspective, IHC solutions should be evaluated in terms of health benefits alongside economic and environmental costs. Although no statistically significant reduction in absenteeism was observed, even modest decreases in infection incidence may be meaningful at the population level, but must be weighed against installation, maintenance, energy use, and material-related environmental impacts. Cost-effectiveness ultimately depends on the magnitude of morbidity reduction, highlighting the need for robust evidence from larger studies.

The Living Lab approach used in this study enabled evaluation under real-world conditions, enhancing ecological validity and practical relevance. The intervention and control units were carefully selected to ensure comparability in terms of building characteristics, environmental conditions, and operational practices. The absence of differences in indoor air quality and water microbiology further supports the comparability of the study units and indicates that the observed trends were unlikely to be driven by baseline environmental differences. However, this approach also introduces variability that cannot be fully controlled, and the relatively small and dynamic human cohort limited statistical power. Due to privacy reasons, we did not have individual data, just monthly averages of number of people and number of infection-related absenteeism. Additional limitations include the lack of blinding, common areas between intervention and control units that may have caused cross-contamination, potential misclassification of infection-related absenteeism based on symptoms rather than confirmed diagnoses, and the absence of viral measurements.

Previous studies by our group have not identified significant adverse effects of antimicrobial coatings on microbial community composition, antimicrobial resistance, or environmental safety under controlled use (Rosenberg et al., 2019; Pietsch et al., 2020; Blomberg et al., 2022; Salonen et al., 2022). Supporting evidence from complementary studies in the same kindergarten setting indicates that TiO₂-based photocatalytic coatings can reduce bacterial load on table surfaces without significantly altering overall microbial community structure (Kaur et al., 2026 preprint). Nevertheless, continued research is required to ensure that wider implementation of such technologies remains safe, effective, and aligned with sustainability goals.

In conclusion, the observations of this study suggest that integrated indoor hygiene solutions may contribute to infection control in real-world kindergarten environments, although the magnitude of the effect remains uncertain. The contribution of the studied antimicrobial surface coatings seems to have no effect on microbial counts. The findings indicate the importance of considering indoor environments as integrated systems in which air, surfaces, water, and human behaviour interact to influence infection risk. Future studies should include larger and more stable participant populations to improve statistical power and enable longitudinal individual-level analyses. It is also important to include viral load measurements in the study and to use study designs that allow for the evaluation of

individual components of the intervention. In addition, comprehensive assessments of long-term sustainability, including economic and environmental impacts, are needed to support evidence-based implementation of indoor hygiene strategies in the built environment.

Data availability statement

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue reservation.

Author contributions

MA: Project administration, Conceptualization, Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Funding acquisition. RM: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Writing – review and editing, Conceptualization. MKi: Data curation, Investigation, Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology. SR: Investigation, Methodology, Writing – review and editing, Formal Analysis, Writing – original draft. JT: Writing – review and editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft. MKu: Investigation, Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft. VA: Writing – review and editing, Supervision. MR: Writing – review and editing, Investigation, Visualization, Data curation. JK: Formal Analysis, Writing – review and editing, Writing – original draft. ML: Writing – review and editing, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration.

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Conflict of interest

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Supplementary material

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fbuil.2026.1875982/full#supplementary-material>

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